

Su'aalaha Qiimeynta Aqoonta, Aragtiyaha, iyo Hab-dhaqannada (KAP) ee fayraska Kaduudiyaha

Qaybta 1aad: Su'aalaha Xogta Bulsho-Dhaqaale (Sociodemographic)

Su'aal	Qaybaha
Immisa jir ayaad tahay?	-----
Waa maxay jinsigaaga?	Dhedig / Lab
Waa maxay xaaladda guurkaaga?	Aan guursan / Guursaday / La furay / Carmal
Waa maxay heerka waxbarashadaada?	Aan wax qorin / Hoose (Primary) / Sare (Secondary) / Jaamacad (Tertiary)
Waa maxay shaqadaada?	Shaqaaale / Beeraley / Arday / Shaqo la'aan

Qaybta 2aad: Aqoonta ku saabsan Fayraska Kaduudiyaha

Lr	Su'aal	Haa	Maya	Ma hubo
1	Ma maqashay hore fayraska Kaduudiyaha (CHIKV)?			
2	Kaduudiyaha waxaa gudbiya kaneeco.			
3	Kaduudiyaha iyo Xumada waa cudur isku mid ah.			
4	Kaduudiyaha waxaa laga qaadi karaa qof ilaa qof kale.			
5	Qandho iyo xanuun kala-goosyada ah waa calaamadaha Kaduudiyaha.			
6	Kaduudiyaha ma laha daawo gaar ah ama tallaal.			
7	Biyaha taagan waxay kordhiyaan taranka kaneecada.			
8	Kaneecada gudbisa Kaduudiyaha waxay qaniintaa maalintii.			

Qaybta 3aad: Aragtiyaha ku saabsan Kaduudiyaha iyo Ka-hortaggiisa

Lr	Weedh	Waan ku raacsanahay	Waan diidanahay	Dhexdhexaad	Si aad ah ayaan ugu raacsanahay	Si aad ah ayaan u diidanahay
1	Kaduudiyaha waa cudur halis ah.					
2	Waxaan aaminsanahay inaan					

	khatar ugu jiro inaan qaado Kaduudiyaha.					
3	Waxaan aaminsanaha y in Kaduudiyaha uu sababi karo dhibaatooyin caafimaad oo muddo dheer ah.					
4	Waxaan aaminsanaha y in xakamaynta kaneecadu ay muhiim u tahay ka hortagga Kaduudiyaha.					
5	Waxaan diyaar u ahay inaan ka qaybqaato ololeyaasha ka hortagga Kaduudiyaha.					

Qaybta 4aad: Hab-dhaqannada Ka-hortagga Kaduudiyaha

Lr	Dhaqan / Ficil	Mar walba	Mararka qaarkood	Marna	
1	Ma isticmaashaa shabaq kaneeco habeenkii?				
2	Ma isticmaashaa dawooyinka kaneecada (repellent) ama buufin?				
3	Ma ka saartaa biyaha taagan agagaarka gurigaaga?				
4	Ma xirataa dhar kaa ilaaliya qaniinyada kaneecada?				
Lr	Su'aal			Haa	Maya
5	Ma raadsatay daryeel caafimaad cudur la xiriira kaneeco sannadkii la soo dhaafay?				

6	Ma heshay waxbarasho caafimaad oo ku saabsan Kaduudiyaha 6-dii bilood ee la soo dhaafay?		
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Section one: Sociodemographic Questions

Questions	Category
What is your age in years?	-----
What is your sex?	Female Male
What is your marital status?	Single Married Divorce widowed
What is your educational status?	Illiterate Primary Secondary Tertiary
What is your occupation?	Employed Farmer Student Unemployed

Section two: Knowledge of Chikungunya Virus Infection Questions

N°	Question / Item	Yes	No	Not sure
1	Have you ever heard of CHIKV?			
2	CHIKV is transmitted by mosquitoes.			
3	CHIKV and Dengue are the same disease.			
4	CHIKV can be transmitted from person to person.			
5	Fever and joint pain are symptoms of CHIKV.			
6	CHIKV has no specific treatment or vaccine.			
7	Standing water increases mosquito breeding.			
8	Mosquitoes that transmit CHIKV bite during the day.			

Section three: Attitudes Toward Chikungunya Virus and Its Prevention Questions

N°	Statement	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly agree	Strongly disagree
1	CHIKV is a serious disease.					
2	I believe I am at risk of getting CHIKV.					
3	I believe CHIKV can lead to long-term health problems.					
4	I believe mosquito control is important in preventing CHIKV.					
5	I am willing to participate in CHIKV prevention campaigns.					

Section four: Preventive Practices Against Chikungunya Virus Infection Questions

N°	Behavior / Practice	Always	Never	Sometimes
1	Do you use mosquito nets at night?			
2	Do you use mosquito repellents or sprays?			
3	Do you eliminate standing water near your home?			
4	Do you wear protective clothing to avoid mosquito bites?			
		Yes	No	
6	Have you sought medical care for mosquito-related illness in the past year?			
7	Have you received any health education about CHIKV in the past 6 months?			